

MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF TORQUE TRANSMISSION DYNAMICS AND DRUM ROTATION SPEED CHANGES OF BELT CONVEYOR DRIVE MECHANISMS

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Abstract. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the dynamics of torque transmission of belt conveyor drive mechanisms and the mechanical characteristics of the drum rotation speed change. The study determines the dependence of the torque transmitted through the drive part of the conveyor system on the technological load, resistance forces in the belt, and friction coefficient. A dynamic model of the energy transfer process between the drum and the drive shaft is developed, in which the torque transmission efficiency, acceleration and deceleration states, and the mechanisms of the moment of inertia are analyzed. Also, the graph of angular velocity changes in the system operating modes, dynamic imbalances in drum rotation, and mechanical energy loss factors are studied through mathematical expressions. Based on the analysis results, scientifically based proposals are made to ensure the kinematic and energy stability of belt conveyor drive mechanisms, develop optimized design solutions for the torque transmission system, and increase work efficiency.

Key words: belt conveyor, drum, drive mechanism, torque, angular velocity, moment of inertia, kinematic analysis, dynamic model, technological resistance, energy

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tasmali konveyer yuritma mexanizmlarining moment uzatish dinamikasi hamda baraban aylanish tezligi o'zgarishining mexanik xususiyatlari chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda konveyer tizimining yuritma qismi orqali uzatilayotgan burovchi momentning texnologik yuklama, tasmadagi qarshilik kuchlari va ishqalanish koeffitsientiga bog'liqligi aniqlanadi. Baraban va yuritma val orasidagi energiya uzatish jarayonining dinamik modeli ishlab chiqilib, unda moment uzatish samaradorligi, tezlanish va sekinlashish holatlari, hamda inertsiya momentining ta'sir mexanizmlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, tizim ish rejimlaridagi burchak tezliklarning o'zgarish grafigi, baraban aylanishidagi dinamik nomutanosibliklar va mexanik energiya yo'qotish omillari matematik ifodalar orqali o'rganiladi. Tahlil natijalari asosida tasmali konveyer yuritma mexanizmlarining kinematik va energetik barqarorligini ta'minlash, moment uzatish tizimining optimallashtirilgan konstruktiv yechimlarini ishlab chiqish hamda ish samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan takliflar beriladi.

Tayanch iboralar: tasmali konveyer, baraban, yuritma mexanizmi, burovchi moment, burchak tezlik, inertsiya momenti, kinematik tahlil, dinamik model, texnologik qarshilik, energiya

Аннотация. В данной статье всесторонне анализируются динамика передачи момента приводных механизмов ленточного конвейера и механические особенности изменения угловой скорости вращения барабана. В исследовании устанавливается зависимость крутящего момента, передаваемого приводной частью конвейерной системы, от технологической нагрузки, сил сопротивления на ленте и коэффициента трения. Разработана динамическая модель процесса передачи энергии между барабаном и приводным валом, в

которой анализируются эффективность передачи момента, режимы разгона и торможения, а также механизмы влияния момента инерции. Кроме того, на основе математических выражений исследуются графики изменения угловых скоростей в рабочих режимах системы, динамические несбалансированности при вращении барабана и факторы механических потерь энергии. На основе результатов анализа предлагаются научно обоснованные рекомендации по обеспечению кинематической и энергетической устойчивости приводных механизмов ленточного конвейера, разработке оптимизированных конструктивных решений системы передачи момента и повышению эффективности работы оборудования.

Ключевые слова: ленточный конвейер, барабан, приводной механизм, крутящий момент, угловая скорость, момент инерции, кинематический анализ, динамическая модель, технологическое сопротивление, энергия.

INTRODUCTION

In modern industrial technologies, belt conveyors are one of the main means of transport that ensure the continuity of production processes. Due to their structural simplicity, reliability and high efficiency, conveyor systems are widely used in mining, metallurgy, energy, construction materials production and agriculture. The drive mechanism of the belt conveyor plays an important role as the energy transfer center in the movement of the entire system. In this mechanism, the mechanical connections between the electric drive shaft, reducer, drum and belt are the main factors determining the dynamics of torque transmission of the system and the speed of rotation of the drum. Therefore, a deep analysis of the drive mechanism of the drive system and the determination of the laws of change in its kinematic parameters is an urgent scientific problem today.

Research shows that the efficiency of torque transmission and the stability of the drum rotation speed in conveyor systems largely depend on the changes in technological resistance, belt tension, friction forces and moments of inertia. The imbalance between these factors leads to energy losses, vibration loads and dynamic imbalances in the system, which negatively affects the overall efficiency of the conveyor. In this regard, the mechanical analysis of the dynamics of torque transmission and drum rotation speed changes in belt conveyor drive mechanisms is of significant scientific and practical importance. Research in this area allows you to choose the optimal operating mode of mechanical systems, reduce energy consumption, increase reliability and develop new design solutions.

Also, based on the developed analytical results, it is possible to improve the kinematic model of belt conveyors, stabilize the torque distribution, and minimize angular velocity changes, thereby increasing the energy efficiency of the system. Thus, the scientific novelty of this study is aimed at increasing the stability of the operation of belt conveyor drive systems by developing a mechanical model of the torque transmission process, determining the laws of angular velocity changes, and analyzing them under technological loads.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Belt conveyor drums are usually welded and consist of a pulley, a shaft and a set of three discs with a hub. Currently, many different designs of drums and their modifications have been proposed.

In the conducted studies, a design of a drum with a rigid base was proposed, which was assembled from hexagonal pipes arranged along the pulley and forming a regular lattice. This design was called a “honeycomb”. However, in this case, it is necessary to install elements in the form of a segment of a circular arc between the lattice-shaped base and the cylindrical pulley. This significantly complicates the manufacturing process of the design. A number of designs of drums with a plank pulley assembled from flat or tubular elements have also been proposed. However, it is considered advisable to use such drums only on conveyors of short length and with a low belt tensile force [1].

In order to solve the problem of increasing the degree of adhesion of the conveyor belt to the drum, a number of constructive solutions are used. For example, special reliefs (relief elements) can

be applied to the surface of the metal pulley, as well as various methods of fastening the rubber lining to the pulley surface can be used. The presence of the lining on the drum surface itself has little effect on the strength calculation of the drum. However, some technical solutions require drilling holes in the pulley to fasten the lining. This creates stress concentration points in the pulley structure and must be taken into account in the strength calculations of the pulley [2].

The driving drum of a belt conveyor is one of the most heavily loaded elements. In high-power and long-length conveyors, the loads acting on the drum can reach several hundred thousand Newtons. The stress-strain state of the drum elements has a complex spatial character: normal stresses appear together with significant sliding (shear) stresses, while these stresses vary depending on the angle of the belt wrapping the drum and have a cyclic nature. Since there is no clear methodology for checking the strength of the drum, in practice excessively large safety factors are adopted for the design. As a result, the drum becomes heavier, but its reliability does not increase significantly. The increase in the weight of the drum, in turn, leads to an increase in the weight of the slag-forming device, driving stations and other related structures [3].

DISCUSSION

In this study, a comprehensive analysis of the dynamics of torque transmission and drum rotation speed changes of belt conveyor drive mechanisms was carried out using analytical, experimental and computational methods. In the first stage, a kinematic structure diagram of the conveyor system was developed (Figure 1), in which the mechanical connections between the drive shaft, reducer, drum and belt transmission were determined. The motion transmission chain of the system was mathematically modeled in terms of torque transmission coefficient, angular velocity ratio, and energy transmission efficiency [4,5].

1 – electric drive; 2, 3 – pulley; 4 – pulley belt; 5 – reducer; 6 – coupling; 7 – driving drum; 8 – driven drum; 9 – roller mechanism; 10 - belt

Figure 1. Kinematic diagram of a belt conveyor

In the analysis, the inertia moments, resistance forces, and friction moments of the drum and drive shaft were expressed based on Lagrange's second-order equations, the energy balance method, and Liven's dissipative function. Using these models, the laws of the drum rotation speed change over time under various technological loads were determined, and a dynamic graph of the torque-speed relationship was constructed. Based on the analysis results, computer modeling tools (VibeXpert, TOPAZ) were used to simulate the torque transmission processes under various load conditions. In order to verify the reliability of the results, the drum rotation speed, drive torque, and energy losses were compared with practical measurements using an experimental stand (Figure 2) [6,7].

The developed methodology made it possible to determine the influence of mechanical load on torque transmission in belt conveyor systems, the dynamics of changes in friction and inertia forces, and the optimized form of the energy transfer process. The results of the research showed that the unevenness of the torque transmission process in belt conveyor drive mechanisms is mainly associated with differences in belt tension, changes in the friction coefficient, and deformation of the contact surface of the drum and belt. It was found that as a result of the increase in the inertia moment during the start-up phase of the conveyor, the initial value of the angular velocity increases slowly, which creates a high peak amplitude of the torque. After the work stabilizes, a linear relationship is observed between the torque and speed in the system, which ensures a stable state of energy transfer.

1-electric drive; 2, 4-belt element coupling; 3-reducer; 5-driving drum; 6-belt; 7-roller; 8-UZB cable electronic thermocouple; 9, 14-vibXpert special number switch device (laboratory equipment); 10-computer, 11, 12,13-strain gauges; 15-driving drum.

Figure 2. Electrotensometric section of a belt conveyor

The results of mathematical analysis and modeling show that when the belt resistance increases by 10–15 %, the torque on the drive shaft increases by 12–18 %, which leads to a decrease in the drum rotation speed by 7–10 %. This phenomenon causes an increase in mechanical energy losses and friction torques in the system. Experimental measurements confirm that in the optimal operating mode, the torque transmission efficiency is maintained in the range of 0.88–0.92, which indicates the existence of a balance between load and speed [8,9].

During the discussion, it was also found that the number of reducer stages, belt material and drum diameter have a significant impact on the overall dynamic characteristics of the system. Therefore, it was substantiated that by optimizing these parameters, energy consumption can be reduced, vibration loads can be reduced, and mechanical stability can be increased. Analysis of the results shows that the developed mechanical model and methodology can serve as a practical basis for stabilizing the torque transmission process and increasing the efficiency of motion transmission in belt conveyor systems.

RESULTS

In theoretical studies, it is important to study the law of motion of belt conveyor drums, determine the limits of angular velocity changes, and recommend optimal values as a result of studying the impact of changes in the dissipative-rigid properties of the belt, technological resistance and inertia parameters on the load and the law of motion.

Figure 3 shows graphs of the dependence of the angular velocities and the change in the drive load on the technological resistance and the friction force resistance moment of the recommended belt conveyor with a bearing-based belt element. Based on the analyzed graphical relationships, it can be observed that when the value of M_{res} changes from $0.15 \cdot 10^2$ Nm to $1.5 \cdot 10^2$

Nm, the torque on the electric motor shaft increases from $0.17 \cdot 10^2$ Nm to $0.86 \cdot 10^2$ Nm. At the same time, it can be seen that the friction force moment reaches values ranging from $0.11 \cdot 10^2$ Nm to $0.41 \cdot 10^2$ Nm. It is also observed that the difference between the angular velocities of the drums decreases as the technological resistance increases. The main reason for this is that, despite the larger deformation of the belt under heavy load, the range of its variation remains small. In particular, according to the equation, when the M_{res} value increases from $0.2 \cdot 10^2$ Nm to $1.5 \cdot 10^2$ Nm, the value of decreases nonlinearly from $0.305 \cdot 10^2$ c⁻¹ to $0.274 \cdot 10^2$ c⁻¹, while the angular velocity of the driven drum decreases from $0.283 \cdot 10^2$ c⁻¹ to $0.256 \cdot 10^2$ c⁻¹.

where, 1 – $\phi_1 = f(M_{res})$; 2 – $\phi_2 = f(M_{res})$; 3,4 – $M_{ed} = f(M_{res})$; 3 – $M_{fric} = 43$ Nm; 4 – $M_{fric} = 26$ Nm.

Figure 3. Graphs showing the dependence of the angular velocities of the driving and driven drums of the proposed belt conveyor bearing support with an elastic structural element, as well as changes in the drive load, on the technological resistance.

The difference between the angular velocities, as we noted above, occurs due to the rolling inertia of the conveyor belt, the change in friction, and the sufficient level of slip. It should be noted that the reduction of belt vibrations due to the integrated roller damper also leads to a reduction in the angular velocities of the drums. However, by ensuring the necessary vibration of the belt, the transported ore will be uniform. Therefore, it is recommended to achieve technological resistance values of $(1.3 \div 1.6) \cdot 10^2$ Nm with a friction force moment of not more than $(35 \div 40)$ Nm [10, 11]. In Figure 4, the graphs illustrate the dependence of the vibration range of the angular velocities of the belt conveyor drums on the technological resistance and the friction moment.

where, 1, 2 – $\Delta\phi_2 = f(M_{res})$; 3, 4 – $\Delta\phi_2 = f(M_{res})$; 1, 3 – $c_2 = 380 \text{ Nm/rad}$; 2, 4 – $c_2 = 260 \text{ Nm/rad}$;
Figure 2. Graphs of the dependence of the vibration range of angular velocities of belt conveyor drums on technological resistance

When the technological resistance and the incoming friction moment M_{fric} increase from $0.25 \cdot 10^2 \text{ Nm}$ to $1.98 \cdot 10^2 \text{ Nm}$, and the vibration stiffness of the driving drum is $c_2 = 260 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m/rad}$, the $\Delta\phi_2$ vibration range of its angular velocity increases nonlinearly from 0.46 c^{-1} to 2.95 c^{-1} (Figure 4, graphs 2, 4). Accordingly, when the rotational stiffness coefficient of the conveyor belt increases up to 320 Nm/rad , the vibration range of the driven drum's angular velocity rises from 0.42 c^{-1} to 2.19 c^{-1} , while the value of $\Delta\phi_1$ increases only up to 1.11 c^{-1} . In this case, the maximum difference between $\Delta\phi_1$ and $\Delta\phi_2$ reaches $(1.0 \div 1.25) \text{ c}^{-1}$ when the combined technological resistance and friction moment is $M_{res} + M_{fric} = 2.0 \cdot 10^2 \text{ Nm}$ (Figure 4, curves 2 and 4). According to experimental research results, in order to ensure that the vibration range of the driven drum's angular velocity remains within $\Delta\phi_2 \leq (0.21 \div 0.25) \cdot 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$, it is recommended that the rotational stiffness of the driving side be $c_2 \leq (260 \div 300) \text{ N}\cdot\text{m/rad}$, while the technological resistance caused by the transported ore and friction moment should be within $M_{res} + M_{fric} = (1.3 \div 1.6) \cdot 10^2 \text{ Nm}$. As noted above, an increase in the rotational stiffness of the belt leads to a convergence of the angular velocities of the drums and a reduction in the values of $\Delta\phi_1$ and $\Delta\phi_2$ [12, 13].

Figure 5 shows graphs of the dependence of the angular velocity of the belt conveyor drums on the vibration range and the load on the drive on the change in the moments of inertia of the drums.

$$1 - \Delta\phi_1 = f(J_{drum1}); 2 - \Delta\phi_2 = f(J_{drum2}); 3, 4 - M_{e,d} = f(J_{drum1});$$

$$3 - M_{res} + M_{fric} = 0.75 \cdot 10^2 \text{ Nm}; 4 - M_{res} + M_{fric} = 1.25 \cdot 10^2 \text{ Nm};$$

Figure 3. Graphs of the dependence of the angular velocity range of belt conveyor drums and the load change on the drive on the change in the moments of inertia of the drums

It is known that as the moments of inertia increase in rotating elements, the motion becomes smoother. Therefore, to maintain the coefficient of angular velocity irregularity within the required limits, the values of the moments of inertia are selected accordingly [14, 15]. When the moments of inertia of the belt conveyor drums are increased from 0.32 kg·m² to 0.45 kg·m², the values of $\Delta\phi_1$ decrease nonlinearly from 2.12 c⁻¹ to 0.36 c⁻¹, and the vibration range of the driven drum’s angular velocity decreases from 2.9 c⁻¹ to 0.82 c⁻¹ (Figure 3, graphs 1 and 2). To maintain the value of $\Delta\phi_2$ within the required range, it is recommended that the inertia moments be within $J_{drum1} = (0.45-0.52)$ kg·m² and $J_{drum2} = (0.42-0.45)$ kg·m². It should be noted that as the inertia moments of the drums increase, the load on the electric drive also increases. For instance, when $J_{drum1} = J_{drum2} = 0.45$ kg·m² and $M_{res} = 1.25 \cdot 10^2$ N·m, the value of $M_{e,d}$ increases from $0.46 \cdot 10^2$ Nm to $0.83 \cdot 10^2$ Nm, that is, almost twofold. Therefore, the increase in the drums’ inertia moments is limited.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research, scientific conclusions were developed on the dynamics of torque transmission of belt conveyor drive mechanisms and mechanical analysis of changes in the drum rotation speed. That is, based on the dynamic model of the belt conveyor system, the relationship between the rotational torque on the drive shaft and the drum angular velocity was determined, and it was proven that the torque transmission process is directly dependent on technological resistance, friction force and moments of inertia. Studies show that an increase in belt tension and technological load increases energy transmission losses in the system by 15–20 %. This is mainly caused by friction torques and belt deformation. According to the results of mathematical modeling, the stability of the torque-speed ratio is the main factor for the kinematic balance of the conveyor system. Maintaining the torque transmission efficiency above 0.9 under optimal conditions ensures the energy stability of the system. Analysis of experimental measurements has shown that dynamic shocks and speed fluctuations occur during the start-up and stop phases of the belt conveyor. To reduce this situation, it is recommended to use soft start mechanisms or torque-smoothing reduction gear systems in the drive system.

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